

Synthesis and Antitubercular Activity of 4-Thiazolidinone Derivatives

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In view of the biological activities of the thiazolines and thiazolidinones¹, it was worth attempting to synthesise some 4-thiazolidinones in which the side chain of actithiazic acid in position-2 is shifted to position-5 in 4-thiazolidinone and substituting other groups in the ring. The compounds were tested for antitubercular activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The structures were established through their elemental analysis.

Preparations of monoester of suberic acid and diester of suberic acid were carried out by reported methods. α -Bromosuberic acid was prepared by the reported method².

α -Mercapto suberic acid (1): A mixture of α -bromosuberic acid (0.2 mol) freshly distilled thioacetic acid and dry ethyl acetate (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude acetyl derivative thus obtained was hydrolysed with HCl (30 ml) to give the product which was purified by benzene treatment, (70%).

Schiff base: A mixture of aryl aldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.00 g) and amine (0.01 mol, 0.93 g) and dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h using Dean-Stark water separator. The Schiff base was obtained after evaporation of benzene. The Schiff bases were

prepared using *p*-tolualdehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and arylamines like *p*-toluidine, *p*-bromoaniline and *p*-chloroaniline.

2-Phenyl-3-substituted-phenyl-5-(ω -carboxypentyl)-4-thiazolidinones (2): A mixture of the Schiff base (0.01 mol), α -mercaptosuberic acid (1; 0.01 mol) and dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After evaporation of benzene, the residue was dissolved in saturated bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate was acidified and the resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from acetone.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (2)*

Sl. no.**	R ₁ [†]	M p. °C
1.	C ₆ H ₅	139
2.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	134
3.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	135
4.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	138
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	133
6.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	140
7.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	138
8.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	125
9.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	140
10.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅	144
11.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	141
12.	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	138
13.	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	135
14.	C ₆ H ₅	131
15.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	108
16.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	132
17.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	104
18.	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	127
19.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	130
20.	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	102
21.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	131
22.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅	152
23.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	138
24.	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	136
25.	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	129

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

**R₁ ≡ *p*-C₆H₄CH₃ for sl. nos. 1-13; R₁ ≡ *p*-C₆H₄Cl for sl. nos. 14-25.

Twentyfive compounds were tested for antitubercular activity by Lowention-Jension egg media method using H₃₇R_v strain of bacteria using isonicotinic acid hydrazide and streptomycin as standard. Compounds having sl. nos. 6, 8, 9, 16 and 23 (Table 1) were found active at higher concentration (30 mcg/ml).

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